

The HuT

Composition of Local DRR Nexus Forums

Deliverable D1.2

DEVELOPED WITHIN

WP1 Demonstrators' Arena, T1.2 Local DRR Nexus Forums

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1. Technical references

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- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

1.1. Document history

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3. Local DRR Nexus Forum (L-DRRnF)

Table 1: The 10 demonstrators

Lead	Location	Country	Area (km ²)	Boundaries	Stakeholders
DEM1 (UPV)	Valencia city	Spain	134 + 29501	Administrative (local government) and physical (2 river basins)	D, H
DEM2 (UPC)	Val d'Aran region	Spain	650	Administrative (regional government)	F, L, S
DEM3 (UNISA)	Lattari mountains	Italy	300	Administrative (local government) and physical (mountain range)	F, FF, L, S
DEM4 (VU)	Vilnius city	Lithuania	401	Administrative (local government)	F
DEM5 (HEREON)	Schleswig-Holstein state and harbour cities	Germany	466 km of coastline	Administrative (regional and local governments)	H, S, F
DEM6 (IMO)	East fjords	Iceland	3500	Administrative (local government) and physical (fjord)	L, S
DEM7 (KOTIVIZIG)	Hungarian Tisza River basin	Hungary	7180	Administrative (regional government) and physical (river basin)	F
DEM8 (CMCC)	Ogliastra province	Italy	1855	Administrative (intermediate local government)	D, FF, H
DEM9 (BGS)	Dorset county	UK	2653	Administrative (intermediate local government)	F, L, S
DEM10 (UNIGE)	Bern canton	Switzerland	5960	Administrative (regional government)	F, L, S

Within The HuT, we consider the Local DRR Nexus Forum as a local platform for diverse stakeholder groups to share their experiences, co-develop solutions in the field of disaster risk reduction (DRR) and climate change adaptation (CCA). This platform is a continuous format for exchange among stakeholders in the setting within a Demonstrator and could consist of a series of activities of co-design, co-development and co-production. The abbreviation of such activities is Local DRR Nexus Forum or L-DRRnF for short.

In doing so, we are creating a nexus between a wide range of local stakeholders in a friendly and stimulating setting in order to build convergence throughout the project duration and the legacy beyond. By building networks of stakeholders with common or diverse interests, we create long-term relationships and trust for transparent dialogue.

3.1. Getting started: a goal-oriented approach

With Deliverable 1.4. we already provided a template additionally with guidelines for the demonstrators. As further guidance was requested, we used the second General Assembly held in Valencia in October 2023 as a venue for in-person exchange with consultation and guidance, and the in-person exercise at the General Assembly was tailor-designed to meet the needs of the Demonstrators. These are the inquiries from Demonstrators we aim to tackle:

“I have been carrying out some stakeholder activities in our demonstrator, but I don’t know how to fill them in the narrative template canvas. Could you show us how to fill in the narrative template canvas?”

“I do not how to get started some of our activities related to L-DRRnF.”

“Could you please use one Demonstrator to show us how to conduct L-DRRnF serving as an exemplar?”

3.2. Roadmap methodology

Responding to the inquiries and needs from the Demonstrators, we selected DEM5 as an example since activities such as a Local DRR Nexus Forum have been carried out within DEM5. To better support the 10 Dems to have a clear vision throughout the projects across different activities in WP1, we have designed a goal-oriented roadmap as a practical approach for implementation in all demonstrators. The objective for each demonstrator is to identify their target group, and from there to discern the Local DRR nexus forum that has already evolved or can still be developed. The roadmap is shown as the picture below and this has been printed and used as a break-out group exercise to test with all Demonstrators at the General Assembly in Valencia. All the Demonstrators participated and gave input to provide insights and details of their previous or planned activities reading their Local DRR Nexus Forums.

Figure 1: Roadmap towards the composition of L-DRRnF

Glückstadt is a pilot city for DEM5. Glückstadt is a harbour city at the North Sea located at the Schlegs-Holstein State. Facing multiple risks such as flooding, sea-level rise, and storm-surges, local stakeholders ranging from the Mayor, citizens, public and private sectors, as well as citizens are concerned about the topic of climate extremes and cascading risks of different hazards. As the following illustration shows, by collaborating with the Mayor of the city and a citizen dialogue facilitation company hired by the Municipality (TOLLER ORT GbR), we were given access to one of Glückstadt's district festivals, where we had a stand to showcase the concept and work of The HuT and additionally, we have carried out science-to-implementation activities across other work packages (WP1 and WP3, such as Local DRR Nexus Forums and serious gaming with visitors of the City Festival in Glückstadt).

Figure 2: The DEM5 roadmap model

Among visitors there were the Mayor, citizens (families, children, older people, associations of people with disability, women's associations). This gave us the opportunity to engage in a two-way dialogue with a wide audience for the Local DRR Nexus Forum in Glückstadt (DEM 5). The overview of the stakeholders engaged also include the local newspaper, municipal art association, different citizen boards of the DEM 5.

Figure 3: Stakeholder engagement in DEM5

3.3. Results

After the illustrated explanation of the roadmap approach for Local DRR Nexus Forum at the framework of the General Assembly, we formed three breakout groups with three different starting target groups to interactively guide the demonstrators towards our intended goal of planning and composing the Local DRR Nexus Forum, as follows:

- Municipality
- Education sector
- Communities

The demonstrators were very keen to cooperate and contribute.

Figure 4: Results of one of the breakout groups at the 2nd General Assembly

The roadmap encouraged demonstrators to take the next step and record their activities using “The Hut for Me and You” template. From this, we were able to extract their activities in relation to the Local DRR Nexus Forums that had already taken place or were in the planning stage. The following figure summarizes the overview of the activities of the Local DRR Nexus Forums in 10 Demonstrators.

Figure 5: DEM's roadmap for the composition of its L-DRRnF

As shown on the figure, all ten Demonstrators have identified their target group of stakeholders and interacted with them. This has shown they have a clear goal for the composition of local DRR nexus forums. The stakeholder groups engaged are diverse: from public sectors (city councils, municipalities, mayors, high schools, civil protection agencies, various associations, and etc.), non-governmental organizations, local communities and citizens, and different local services. Three Demonstrators (DEMs 3, 6, and 7) have additionally carried out interviews to also gain knowledge to develop specific activities or services for their implementation activities, such as web platform/App for early warning systems. This also additionally serves as a cluster for mutual learning for other Demonstrators and can be upscaled beyond the project scope. Nine out of ten Demonstrators have carried out their local DRR nexus forums. The one who has not carried out the local DRR nexus forum yet, has also planned activities for the next months. Additionally, the Demonstrators as well as scientific partners have shared and are also supporting each other for mutual learning and experience sharing. The further illustrations with synthesis will be explained in the next sub-chapter of results.

The goal-oriented method of a roadmap illustration as an incentive tool for the workshops mentioned above successfully guided the demonstrators to document their activities towards the Local DRR Nexus Forum.

4. Detailed planning or composition

4.1. Realized Local DRR Nexus Forums

From the template and regular reporting (logbook) could be derived that every demonstrator already started to set up their target group and almost all of them already held Local DRR Nexus Forums with main stakeholders.

The 10 Demonstrators have docked with three different local groups to interact as part of The Human-Tech Nexus. These are located in the following areas:

- local municipalities
- universities / schools
- local communities / citizens associations

The majority of demonstrators first approached their city councils or local authorities. These acted as door openers for future Local DRR Nexus Forums. Many have gained access to local workshops and stakeholder meetings through their “start-up” groups focussing the main challenges in their arena. Other activities done in the first project year include personal training, a district festival, and serious game sessions. Alongside with the activities, three demonstrators (DEM 3, DEM 6, DEM 7) started to develop website platforms, mobile apps, and new early warning systems to provide citizens with online access to information on natural hazards and risks in their area.

Of particular note is the DEM3 roadmap from starting in secondary school/university to participating in a science week as an achieved Local DRR Nexus Forum. As part of the 2nd General Assembly, DEM1 developed an interdisciplinary exhibition on art and science in public spaces, the Valencia Botanical Garden, in collaboration with the UPV Faculty of Design.

4.2. Local DRR Nexus Forum in planning

Some demonstrators are planning a Local DRR Nexus Forum to further engage local stakeholders. Examples are from DEM3 and DEM10, who are planning to develop serious games on local risks and awareness raising in the vulnerable area.

Workshops with local stakeholders will continue, e.g. DEM8 will organise several workshops on different topics such as prevention strategies, communication and science, and financial instruments in order to develop a common fire risk management strategy. DEM5 is also planning a brainstorming session with citizens and the local administration on storm surge strategies.

DEM4, whose elections will take place in 2024, plans to take the opportunity to engage local stakeholders and raise their awareness about urban flooding in Vilnius. In addition, DEM4 will collect and disseminate information on existing climate-related events in order to develop climate-proof design of drainage networks and emergency response in case of heavy rainfall or urban flooding.

4.3. Conclusion

90% of the demonstrators already did their first Local DRR Nexus Forum and the rest plan to have their first forum next year. In the first project year, most of the demonstrators had the Local DRR Nexus Forum through workshops and meetings with local stakeholders. Most of the demonstrators plan to continue their progress, disseminate the information, raise awareness among citizens about local hazards and multi-risks, and develop strategies and innovative tools to help citizens be better prepared for extreme events.

5. The way forward

This deliverable shows the composition of local DRR nexus forums at the ten Demonstrators. According to the project planning, the demonstrators have to carry out the first local nexus forum activity by the month 18. The results have shown that the achievement rate at the month 15 is with a very successful rate of 90%, and until month 18 all ten Demonstrators will already have their local DRR nexus forum activities carried out. These activities are regularly reported also through the internal logbook and newsletters for constant exchange. We will continue to stimulate constant exchange for further mutual learning and this effective platform format of Local-DRR Nexus Forum will continue until the end of the project.

